

visStatistics

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```
library(visStatistics)
```

Abstract

The R package `visStatistics` provides means to quickly visualize and analyze raw data.

Based on a decision tree it picks the statistical hypothesis test with the highest statistical power between the dependent variable (response) named `varsample` and the independent variable (feature) named `varfactor` in a `data.frame` named `dataframe`. A minimal function call has the structure:

```
visstat(dataframe, varsample, varfactor)
```

Data in the provided `dataframe` must be structured column wise, where `varsample` and `varfactor` are the character strings of the column names of the dependent and independent variable respectively.

The choice of statistical tests performed by the core function `visstat()` depends on the type of the data (quantitative numerical or qualitative categorical), the number of levels whilst dealing with categorical data and the data distributions.

`visStatistics` offers a fully automated workflow that is especially suited for browser-based interfaces to server-based deployments of R. It has been successfully applied for unbiased analysis of medical raw data.

The remainder of this vignette focuses on the the algorithm underlying the decision tree of `visstat()`, whilst a call to `?visstat` documents all parameter settings of the function.

Comparing means and medians

If the feature `varfactor` is a categorical variable (in R a `factor`) with two or more levels and the response `varsample` is numeric, tests are applied to compare the means or medians of the samples.

Two sample tests: Welch's t-Test or Wilcoxon rank sum test

If the independent variable `varfactor` has two levels and the dependent variable `varsample` is numeric, either Welch's t-Test or the Wilcoxon rank sum test are performed. The choice follows the algorithm:

- If the sample size for both levels is bigger than 100, perform always the `t.test()` (Lumley et al. 2002).
- If the sample size of at least one of the levels is smaller than 100, checks first for normality of both distributions with the Shapiro-Wilk Normality Test (`shapiro.test()`):

- If the p-values in the `shapiro.test()` of both samples are bigger than the error probability `1-conf.level`, Welch's t-Test (`t.test()`) is executed.
- If the p-values of both samples in the `shapiro.test()` are smaller than the error probability `1-conf.level`, a Wilcoxon rank sum test (`wilcox.test()`) is executed.

The graphical representation consists of box plots overlaid with jitter plots showing each data point. In the case of the `t.test()`, additionally `theconf.level*100 %`-confidence intervals are shown. The test statistics of the chosen test as well as the summary statistics of the generated boxplots is generated and returned as a list.

Examples

```
mtcars$am = as.factor(mtcars$am)
tttestStatistics = visstat(mtcars, "mpg", "am")
```


Welch's t-test calling `t.test()`

```
# uncommenting the next line prints out test statistics
# tttestStatistics
```

```
#Increasing the confidence level
tttestStatistics = visstat(mtcars, "mpg", "am", conf.level = 0.99)
```



```
grades_gender <- data.frame(
  Sex = as.factor(c(rep("Girl", 20), rep("Boy", 20))),
  Grade = c(19.3, 18.1, 15.2, 18.3, 7.9, 6.2, 19.4,
            20.3, 9.3, 11.3, 18.2, 17.5, 10.2, 20.1, 13.3, 17.2, 15.1, 16.2, 17.3,
            16.5, 5.1, 15.3, 17.1, 14.8, 15.4, 14.4, 7.5, 15.5, 6.0, 17.4,
            7.3, 14.3, 13.5, 8.0, 19.5, 13.4, 17.9, 17.7, 16.4, 15.6))

wilcoxonStatistics = visstat(grades_gender, "Grade", "Sex")
```

Wilcoxon rank sum exact test p-value = 0.11

median Grade of Girl equals median Gr

Wilcoxon rank sum test (calling `wilcox.test()`)

More than two samples: One Way Test and ANOVA or Kruskal-Wallis-Test

If the categorical (`factor`) variable `varfactor` has more than two levels and the response `varsample` is numeric, the underlying assumptions of the analysis of variance, normality of the standardized residuals and homoscedacity, are checked by the function `vis_anova_asumptions()`.

Residual analysis

It checks for the normality of the standardised residuals of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) fit generated by the function `aov()`. To do so it applies both the Shapiro-Wilk-test `shapiro.test()` and the Anderson-Darling-Test `ad.test()` on the standardized residuals. Furthermore the data is graphically analysed by plotting the standardized residuals versus the fitted mean values of the linear model for each level of `varfactor`. Additionally the normal QQ plot of the standardized residuals is generated.

Check for homogeneity of variances in each level: Bartlett test

Both `aov()` and `oneway.test()` check, whether two or more samples from normal distributions have the same mean. Whereas `aov()` requires homogeneity of variances in each level (group), the `oneway.test()` does not assume that the variances in each group are necessarily equal. Homoscedacity is tested with the `bartlett.test()`. It performs Bartlett's test of the null hypothesis that the variances in each of the levels are the same.

One Way Test and ANOVA

Depending on the p-value of the `bartlett.test()` the appropriate test is shown in the title:

- If the p-value of the `bartlett.test()` is bigger than `1-conf.level`, we can assume homogeneity of variances in each level (group) and the p-values of `aov()` is displayed.
- Otherwise homoscedacity can not be assumed and the p-value of `oneway.test()` is reported.

To generate Sidak corrected confidence intervals, we calculate the corrected probability of error for the construction of M confidence intervals,

$$\alpha_{Sidak} = 1 - conf.int^{1/M}.$$

Here, M is the number of levels of the independent variable (Šidák 1967). Inserting the corrected α_{Sidak} into the standard formula for confidence intervals we obtain the Sidak corrected boundaries of the confidence interval

$$\left[\bar{x} - t_{(1-\frac{\alpha_{Sidak}}{2}; n-1)} \frac{s}{\sqrt{n}} ; \bar{x} + t_{(1-\frac{\alpha_{Sidak}}{2}; n-1)} \frac{s}{\sqrt{n}} \right],$$

where \bar{x} is the mean, s the standard deviation and n the number of entries of each group (level).

Note that the current structure of `visstat()` does not allow the study of interactions between the different levels of the independent variable.

Post-hoc analysis: Tukey Honest Significant Differences We use the Tukey Honest Significant Differences `TukeyHSD()` to create a set of confidence intervals on the differences between the means of the levels of a factor with the specified family-wise probability `conf.level`. This list of confidence intervals accompanied by the adjusted p-values is returned. If the difference between two levels is significant at the given `conf.level`, the displayed letters at the bottom of the graph between the two levels will differ. Note that the Tukey HSD requires homoscedacity of the samples. In a future revision of `visStatistics` an appropriate post-hoc test for non homogeneous data will be included.

Kruskal-Wallis-Test

If the p-values of the standardized residuals calculated by `shapiro.test()` or `ad.test()` are smaller than the error probability `1-conf.level`, a normal distribution of the residuals can not be assumed. In this case, `visstat()` chooses a non-parametric alternative, the Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test. `kruskal.test()` tests the null that the medians are the same in each group (level). As post-hoc-analysis the pairwise Wilcoxon rank sum test `pairwise.wilcox.test()` applying the default Holm method for multiple comparisons (Holm 1979) is used. If the Holm corrected p-value for a pair is smaller than `1-confint`, the green letters below the corresponding two box plots will differ. Otherwise the graphical representation of the Kruskal-Wallis test is analogue to the above described Wilcoxon rank sum test. A list with the test statistics of the Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test as well as the p-values of the pairwise comparisons adjusted by the Holm method is returned.

Examples

The `npk` data sets reports the yield of peas in pounds/block on 6 blocks.

```
oneway_npk = visstat(npk, "yield", "block")
```

Check for homogeneity of variances: Bartlett Test, $p = 0.042$
 Check for normality of standardized residuals: Shapiro-Wilk: $p = 0.12$
 Anderson-Darling: $p = 0.16$

std. Residuals vs. Fitted

Normal Q-Q Plot

One way test

One-Way test $p = 0.012$

The post-hoc analysis with `TukeyHSD()` reveals no significant difference between the yield in all blocks (all green letters are the same). #### ANOVA

To stabilize the variance we transform the count data with the square root.

```
InsectSprays_tr = InsectSprays
InsectSprays_tr$count = sqrt(InsectSprays$count)
visstat(InsectSprays_tr, "count", "spray")
```

Check for homogeneity of variances: Bartlett Test, $p = 0.59$
Check for normality of standardized residuals: Shapiro–Wilk: $p = 0.68$
Anderson–Darling: $p = 0.75$

std. Residuals vs. Fitted

Normal Q–Q Plot

ANOVA $p = 6.3e-20$

In the above example the scatter plots of the standardized residuals, the QQ -plot and the p-values of both Shapiro-Wilk-test and Anderson-Darling tests are greater than the probability of error $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore we can assume that the residuals are normally distributed. At the given confidence level the homogeneity of variances can not be assumed ($p < \alpha$ as calculated with the `bartlett.test()`), and the p-value of the `oneway.test()` is displayed.

Kruskal-Wallis rank sum test The iris data set gives the measurement of the petal width in cm for three different iris species.

```
visstat(iris, "Petal.Width", "Species")
```

Check for homogeneity of variances: Bartlett Test, $p = 3.1e-09$
Check for normality of standardized residuals: Shapiro-Wilk: $p = 0.0039$
Anderson-Darling: $p = 9.8e-05$

std. Residuals vs. Fitted

Normal Q-Q Plot

Kruskal–Wallis rank sum test $p = 3.26e-29$

In the iris data example, both the graphical analysis by the scatter plots of the standardized residuals and the QQ -plot as well as the p-values of Shapiro-Wilk-test and Anderson-Darling test suggest that we can not assume that the residuals are normally distributed. Therefore `visstat` switches to the non parametric alternative `kruskal.test()`.

Linear Regression

If the feature `varfactor` and the response `varsample` have only one level of type `numerical` or `integer`, `visstat()` performs a simple linear regression

Residual analysis

`visstat` checks the normal distribution of the standardized residuals derived from `lm()` both graphically and with the Shapiro-Wilk- and Anderson-Test (analogue to section `@ref(aov)`). If the p-values of the null that the standardized residuals are normally distributed of both Shapiro-Wilk and Anderson-Test are greater than `1-conf.int`, the title of the residual plot will display the message “Requirements regression not met.”

Independent of the residual analysis outcome, `visstat()` performs in the subsequent step the regression itself. The title of the graphical output lists the chosen confidence level `conf.level`, the regression parameter accompanied by their confidence levels and p-values as well as the adjusted R^2 . The graph shows the raw data, the regression line and both the confidence and prediction bands corresponding to the chosen `conf.level`. The function returns a list with the test statistics of the linear regression, the p-values of the normality tests of the standardized residuals and the pointwise estimates of the confidence and prediction band.

Example

`cars`

The cars data set reports the speed in mph of cars and the distances (dist) in ft taken to stop.

```
linreg_cars = visstat(cars, "dist", "speed")
```

Residual Analysis
Shapiro–Wilk: $p = 0.022$
Anderson–Darling: $p = 0.036$
Requirements regression not met

$y = a \cdot x + b$, confidence level = 0.95 , adjusted R2 = 0.64
slope a = 3.9 , conf. interval [3.1 , 4.8] , p = 1.5e-12
intercept b = -18 , conf. interval [-31 , -4] , p = 0.012

Increasing the confidence level `conf.level` from the default 0.95 to 0.99 leads to wider confidence and prediction bands:

```
linreg_cars = visstat(cars, "dist", "speed", conf.level = 0.99)
```

Residual Analysis
Shapiro-Wilk: $p = 0.022$
Anderson-Darling: $p = 0.036$

std. Residuals vs. Fitted

Normal Q-Q Plot

$y = a \cdot x + b$, confidence level = 0.99 , adjusted R2 = 0.64
 slope $a = 3.9$, conf. interval [2.8 , 5] , $p = 1.5e-12$
 intercept $b = -18$, conf. interval [-36 , 0.55] , $p = 0.012$


```

#Extract the test statistics
linreg_cars$anderson_darling_test_residuals
#>
#> Anderson-Darling normality test
#>
#> data: rstandard(lm(y ~ x))
#> A = 0.8005, p-value = 0.03555
linreg_cars$shapiro_test_residuals
#>
#> Shapiro-Wilk normality test
#>
#> data: rstandard(lm(y ~ x))
#> W = 0.94518, p-value = 0.0217

```

The linear regression model explains 64% of the total variance of the dependent variables distance named “dist.” p-values greater than `conf.level` in both Anderson-Darling normality test and the Shapiro-Wilk test of the standardized residuals suggest that the normality assumption underlying the linear regression is met.

trees

The trees data set provides measurements of the diameter (named “Girth”) in inches and height in feet of black cherry trees.

```
linreg_cars = visstat(trees,"Height","Girth",conf.level = 0.9)
```

Residual Analysis
Shapiro-Wilk: $p = 0.66$
Anderson-Darling: $p = 0.55$

std. Residuals vs. Fitted

Normal Q-Q Plot

$y = a \cdot x + b$, confidence level = 0.9 , adjusted R2 = 0.24
 slope $a = 1.1$, conf. interval [0.51 , 1.6] , $p = 0.0028$
 intercept $b = 62$, conf. interval [55 , 69] , $p = 1.5e-14$

Both the graphical analysis of the standardized residuals and p-values smaller than `conf.level` in the Anderson-Darling normality test and the Shapiro-Wilk test of the standardized residuals suggest that the condition of normally distributed residuals of the regression model is not met. Furthermore the linear regression model explains only 24% of the total variance of the dependent variables “Height” of the cherry trees. The user should might consider other regression models. This further tests are not provided by `visstat()`.

χ^2 - and Fisher Test

If both the feature `varfactor` and the response are `varsample` are categorical of type `factor`, `visstat` performs a test for the independence of count data. Based on Cochran’s rule (Cochran 1954), either a χ^2 - or a Fisher Test are performed: - If more than 20 percent of all cells have a count smaller than 5, `fisher.test()` is performed and displayed, otherwise the `chisqu.test()`.

In both cases a grouped column charts with the p-value of the corresponding test in the title and a mosaic plot showing Pearson’s residuals (for details see documentation of function `mosaic()` in the `vcd` package) are generated.

Transforming contingency tables

Count data are often presented as multidimensional arrays, so called contingency tables, whereas `visstat()` requires a `data.frame` with a column structure. Arrays can be transformed to this column wise structure with the helper function `counts_to_cases()`

Example

```
HairEyeColorDataFrame = counts_to_cases(as.data.frame(HairEyeColor))
```

Pearson's Chi-squared test and mosaic plot with Pearson residuals

```
HairEyeColorDataFrame = counts_to_cases(as.data.frame(HairEyeColor))  
visstat(HairEyeColorDataFrame, "Hair", "Eye")
```


Fisher's exact test and mosaic plot with Pearson residuals

```
HairEyeColorMaleFisher = HairEyeColor[, , 1]
#slicing out a 2 x 2 contingency table
blackBrownHazelGreen = HairEyeColorMaleFisher[1:2, 3:4]
blackBrownHazelGreen = counts_to_cases(as.data.frame(blackBrownHazelGreen));
fisher_stats = visstat(blackBrownHazelGreen, "Hair", "Eye")
```



```
# fisher_stats #uncommenting prints out summary statistics
```

Saving the graphical output

The generated graphs can be saved in the file formats supported by `Cairo()`: “png,” “jpeg,” “pdf,” “svg,” “ps” and “tiff.” In the following example we save the graphics files in the output format “png” to the `plotDirectory` `tempdir()`. The applied naming convention of the graphics file reflects the chosen statistical test and the variable names.

```
visstat(blackBrownHazelGreen,"Hair","Eye",graphicsoutput = "png",plotDirectory =
tempdir())
```

Remove the graphical output from `plotDirectory`

```
file.remove(file.path(tempdir(),"chi_squared_or_fisher_Hair_Eye.png"))
#> [1] TRUE
file.remove(file.path(tempdir(),"mosaic_complete_Hair_Eye.png"))
#> [1] TRUE
```

Overview of implemented tests

`t.test()`, `wilcox.test()`, `aov()`, `kruskal.test()`, `lm()`, `fisher.test()`, `chisqu.test()`

Implemented tests to check the normal distribution of standardized residuals

`shapiro.test()` and `ad.test()`

Implemented post-hoc tests

`TukeyHSD()` for `aov()` and `pairwise.wilcox.test()` for `kruskal.test()`.

Bibliography

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